

NATURE AND WISE. THE ROLE OF PROVERBS ABOUT WATER IN
NATURE

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Abstract: Currently, in order to improve the quality and efficiency of the educational process in higher and secondary education, in the implementation of the State Education Standards, Geography is provided with a curriculum and textbooks, along with all general education subjects. Pedagogical technologies are being implemented. Tested methods show their effectiveness in students' careful mastering of the content of geographical objects, events and processes presented in DTS, in learning about cause and effect connections. Increasing students' interest by using innovative technologies and several types of interactive methods in the course of the lesson is one of the priority tasks for all pedagogues. Using the "Nature and Wisdom" method during each lesson, like different methods, leads students to research, to have a different attitude to nature and the environment, and to love science. Among them, the place of proverbs and wisdom about water is incomparable. Water is a natural gift and it is our duty not to waste it.

Keywords: torrent, flood, chill, water, stream, stream, river, Geographical culture, modern pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, natural gift.

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Geography is the only science aimed at providing information to create a complete picture of the earth, the planet where humanity lives. The role of folk proverbs, which have been considered the "gem of words" of the people for thousands of years, is incomparable in the formation of geographical culture in students.

The development of human social life has left a very valuable, valuable and useful heritage from the early stages of its development. Today we call this heritage as values.

Values are the traditions, rituals, proverbs, proverbs and advice of our people. Proverbs and sayings have a special place among them. It has a very deep scientific and practical significance created by the people. These have been polished over the past years and periods and turned into compact spiritual masterpieces.

Today, the independence of our Republic requires the full use of the cultural heritage of our people in the path of enlightenment.

The role of folk proverbs in teaching the science of geography is incomparable, because proverbs and wise words are the cream of wisdom and words of praise of our ancestors. The skillful use of folk proverbs during the teaching of science contributes to the development of a young, mature generation as a hardworking,

noble, humble person - in a word, a mature person with a mature spirituality and full of positive qualities. .

Literature means the art of words and geography. And proverbs contain the subtle experiences of the human heart and broad observations of life. Proverbs is a very simple word, but it is a huge and complex word. A lot of artistic labor and talent of generations was spent in their creation. Folk proverbs used in the science of geography are a necessary tool for our speech to express events and processes clearly and figuratively.

"Geography - philosophy of regions". This sentence reveals the entire existence philosophically and encourages the reader to think more broadly. Applying the **"Nature and Wise"** method during the lesson, using such proverbs, increases the effectiveness of the lesson and helps students to master geographical knowledge. , covers the topics of the months of the year, animals, plants, agriculture and animal husbandry.

"Where there is water, there is life"

"Water has come - light has come."

The ancient sages of the East believe that water is the oldest gift of God, one of the most vital necessities for human existence. Water is a symbol of life, living and renewal, reproduction. Thanks to water, beautiful gardens are built, wheat fields that shine like gold, and water is the creator of millions of tons of white gold. The main content of the existence of all beings and beings is water. It is correct to say that the advice and conclusions embodied in it are a program of spiritual support for human life and living. That's why one of the scholars of the East, Mirza Bedil, assessed proverbs and wisdom as "the key of the people". Today, every wisdom contains content and conclusions aimed at education and upbringing. Analysis of their content shows that there are more than a hundred sayings related to nature alone. Notes and wisdom in them are aimed at protecting and protecting all components of animate and inanimate nature, encouraging a neat and healthy lifestyle, indicating the level of ecological comfort of places.

Our wise and creative nation has left not only its cultural, historical and social wealth to the current generation, but also the spiritual and spiritual treasures that have the gulshan of thought. Among them, folk proverbs from the oral works of our forefathers deserve special appreciation and recognition as a treasure trove of treasures. The emergence of folk proverbs is related to a certain period, geographical environment, economic and political conditions.

Proverbs are so rich in content that all aspects of society and social life are reflected in them.

Every nation accumulates a lot of life experience over the centuries and passes this experience on to future generations through various means. Proverbs and wise

words are considered our priceless spiritual heritage. There is no nation in the world that has not created masterpieces of wisdom.

Professor G. Vambery, a well-known European orientalist, wrote as he wrote after returning from his trip to our country in the second half of the last century: No one should be surprised that this passion is stronger than that of the members of educated society in Paris or London. Proverbs and wisdom can be found in the written language as well as in the living language. he always listens to the story with a serious expression on his face. No rational statement, no persuasive word that contradicts the meaning of the proverb, can affect his mind, his innate proportionality in nature is not related to anything left by his ancestors and them. It is not manifested in such a strong taste for anything other than a strong and firm belief in the wisdom of wisdom and that it is not spoken incorrectly.

Wise is a whole book, a philosophical worldview. Every nation accumulates a lot of life experience over the centuries, and leaves this experience as a legacy to the next generation through various means.

The Uzbek people are one of those peoples. For the development of world culture, the wisdom of our people's culture, which produced many thinkers such as Al-Khorazmi, Abu-Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Mirza Ulug`bek, Alishr Navoi, Babur Mirza, has long been shown. Proverbs encourage a person to be diligent, to do educational work, to be humane, and also to understand life, existence, as it is, in its entirety. As with other sciences, there are many proverbs and sayings related to the science of geography.

Ex: "Geography and philosophy of regions"

"The map is the window of reality", "The map is the second language of geography"

Making proverbs and sayings successful is the way of gradual development of social development, the customs of our people, the specific aspects of all professions and trades, the weapons used in them, every animal, animal world, how many plants in the world of plants. It requires detailed knowledge of its specific features, the laws of natural phenomena, many aspects of medicine, the ideology of Islam, philosophical concepts, and the total aspects of life.

Nature is the environment in which people live. Geography is the only academic subject aimed at providing information to create a complete picture of the Earth. This science teaches natural and social economic processes and phenomena occurring on the earth.

Proverbs about nature teach logical ideas about the means and methods of improving the natural landscape of the globe, increasing production efficiency, living standards of the population, and environmental conditions, and gain a lot of importance.

These wisemen teach people natural culture, which is a component of universal culture. Folk proverbs used in nature are considered a necessary tool for our speech to express events and processes in a clear, clear and figurative way. Among the wisdoms about nature, the wisdoms related to water occupy an important place. In wisdom about water, it is recommended to effectively use folk wisdom about water, its value, the river, its regime, concepts and laws, and natural phenomena. In Proverbs, information is given about the relief of the place, its features, the main reliefs, mountains, depressions, plains, oases, and hills. It is important to convey these concepts and events to the reader through folk wisdom.

It is known that in natural geography there are separate topics about atmospheric precipitations and their causes. Our wise man created folk proverbs and wisdom based on his thousand years of experience about atmospheric precipitation and their benefits and harms.

In these wisemen, natural phenomena, rain, wind, water and other processes are presented clearly and succinctly. Because folk proverbs were created for thousands of years, the names of the months are old-fashioned. It is known that in nature "the rotation of the Earth around the sun" causes the appearance of seasons and months. These processes are among the wisdoms and open the door of great importance for a person.

In wise created by the people related to nature, it fully reflects the cause and effect relationships of natural, social and economic phenomena in terms of space and time. Folk proverbs on the topic of nature are a very necessary tool for the student to express his thoughts clearly, vividly and figuratively. Knowledge of the different types of plants and animals on the surface of the earth, their interrelationship and interaction, their uneven distribution on the surface of the earth, human influence on plants and animals, domestic animals and cultivated plants. and insights are gained.

In the study of folk proverbs and wisdom related to farming, animal husbandry, horticulture and land cultivation, the use of folk proverbs and wisdom collected by our people over thousands of years, the basic concepts and the content of the main events and processes appropriate to the topic. helps to understand. There are many meaningful words related to nature in proverbs, which show human labor, heart, love for nature, and observations. Proverbs are a necessary educational tool for the content of geographical events and processes to reach the student clearly.

- "Where there is water, there is life"

In a series of proverbs, the ancestors advise that water, known as the "water of life", is a precious thing for the life of humanity and nature, that it should be valued, saved, and kept clean without pollution.

"Dearer than water and gold",

A land without water is a grave, a land with water is a flower garden.

"Water jeweler, water jeweler"

"Water has come, light has come"

"El's life is with earth, Earth's life is with water",

"Don't spit in the drinking well",

"Don't spit in the well, go back and drink" " is used in the meaning.

No matter which geographical proverb or wisdom you take, it always evaluates reality either from a sharply positive or a sharply negative point of view. This opens the way for the proverb to spread quickly and widely.

"He drinks honey at the beginning of the river, poison at the end."

This wise word has a very deep meaning. In order to understand this saying, first of all, we need to know what a river is. The river-basin is called a watercourse flowing in a natural channel, saturated with surface and underground water generated by the rains. In this case, the fact that the river basin is a special place, the water at the beginning is very clean and pure, and finally, the pollution of the water on the downstream side of the river due to the economic activities of the people, is clearly stated. The aunts living in the river's confluence have to satisfy their needs with this garbage-filled water.

"Water is gold, water is gold."

Water is of great importance in the creation of all the things that are built by human hands for the survival of nature. In the hot summer days, they feel that water is a unique pearl, more valuable than gold for all living beings. "Just as the jeweler knows the value of gold, the waterman knows the value of water." A wide cotton garden is like a jeweler watering the growing cotton buds. A jeweler is a rare and precious thing, he is the owner of a unique profession who makes various miraculous items, decorations and jewels from gold and precious pearls. The items he made are valuable, and we cherish them. So water is as valuable as these pearls, and water is as precious as jewels, zero isn't it actually water that grows this pearl? Therefore, it is necessary for us to appreciate water and not allow it to be polluted.

"Spitting in the water"

Water is clean, pure and clear miracle. It has great power to quench thirst. Like a stain on this great blessing, some people pollute it and spit it out, but this is considered a sin against Islam. he should be able to protect himself from contamination of the great blessing that satisfies his needs. Harming it means harming our health.

"It is halal if the water is rolled yet"

Water is a symbol of clarity and purity. Honesty is one of the great human qualities. Man and water are a noble concept. As the German artist Henrich Heide said, "Honesty dies when it is sold. We are far from the place where we live, we are

in a barren desert or We are walking on top of Purviqor mountains. We are very, very thirsty. Then a strange thing - water - comes out in front of us, but I say drink, hurry - hurry and get fat, something won't let me. My companion repeatedly says "drink" to me, and then to calm my mind, "enough water" "If I drink it, I believe that water is a precious blessing and a symbol of life. Let's give an example of the custom of the Uzbek people to drink it three times and then put it down." let's give an example of the custom of pouring it into a cup three times. Pouring it into a cup three times and putting it back into the kettle is six times in total.

"Chilla water - gold water"

In this article, it is recommended to irrigate the crops during the summer period (from June 25 to August 5), and to water the soil during the winter period (from December 25 to February 5). . Many years of experience of grandfather farmers, both of these events are of great importance in the production of abundant crops. "Chilla is the blood of the earth", the land irrigated in Chilla, the garden produces abundant grapes.

"You can't flood a beautiful place"

"Flood" - sandstone, mixed muddy flood water that flows rapidly as a result of snowfall and hail in the spring.

Floods come with great speed and cause damage to many places. If there are more trees or closer to each other, the flood moves slowly and stops moving there. Trees reduce the movement of floods and protect the land from being washed away. Trees protect the areas there from floods.

"The building on the Samarkand river,

One day there will be looting by pressing the button."

"Shower" is a large drop, strong, torrential rain. In the spring and early summer, the activity of cyclones increases greatly, when the rising air flow accelerates, it rains when the cool front of the cyclone passes.

"Stream" - a waterway formed by floods, hailstorms, rains, differs in size from a ditch and a waterway that has appeared naturally without human labor. The increase of water in the stream also occurs as a result of these yogins. That is why the houses built near the stream are considered a deposit, because they can be destroyed by floods in early spring and autumn. Floods occur as a result of heavy rains.

"Water is a dumb beast"

"Grass and water - tongueless beast",

"The work of water is to blow, the work of grass is to burn."

"The appearance of the water is gentle and calm (although the water is slow, gentle, carefree, it is said that it will drown a person who does not know how to swim and who is not careful)"

Too little water is a problem, too much is a problem."

"**The river is safe, the river is a disaster**" (river-grape). They emphasized the safety of water and grass and stressed the need to take measures to prevent it.

"**The hunter's death is in the hunt, the waterman's death is in the water**"

"**Don't cross the sea and drown in the stream**",

"**Save yourself from the plague of grass and water.**"

"**You can't cover the water-soaked dust with a hat.**"

"**If you don't dig a ditch, water won't come out**"

They say that a man's eyebrows are better than the earth's ditches. In the spring, ditches are weeded and cleaned, water flows and the ditches are blocked with sand. Water flows from the ground. Our motherland also comes alive in an instant.

"**Ditch to water - light to the road**",

As they say, "It's easy to sow crops, but it's hard to bring water." If we want to go somewhere, we immediately go on the road, because the roads lead us to our destination, and the ditch is the waterway.

"A brave person brings water, everyone sows crops" (in the past, it was not a difficult task to dig a canal to bring water. This situation is reflected in the proverb). At this point, I thought it is permissible to tell a legend and a story related to digging a ditch. In ancient times, there was a man named Shahpur, who dug a ditch in the middle of the desert and brought water. Gradually, the land around it was turned into arable fields, and people moved in and built houses for themselves. Thus, Shafirkon, one of the districts of Bukhara region, was born. -is actually the word "kand" and means "dug" in Persian, that is, "**Shahpurkand**" means "**Shohpur dug**".

"**If water does not flow from the ditch, bread will not flow from the basket**"

"**Water comes in the dream of a thirsty person**",

"**Look for water under the sand**",

"Where there is sand, there is water, and where there is water, there is life." Such admonitions were used to get rid of dehydration and thirst in deserts and deserts.

"**If you ask for water, ask from Solomon.**"

All the main canals, which play a major role in the economic life of the Khorezm oasis, are connected with the name of one or another saint. Sometimes such a saint is valued as the patron of the canal, and sometimes as the person who miraculously released water from Amudarya and was the direct founder of the canal. Saint Suleiman was considered the patron of the canal network on the south side of Khanka.

"**Spring carries the water of the river,**

Work increases human value.

In spring, the season of living of our country, the rains and snows that fell throughout the year melt from the mountains and pour into the rivers. As a result, water increases and the level rises. It is said that the water of the river overflows in the spring for this phenomenon to happen in the spring. In reality, the increase of this water occurs as a result of rainfall. If we come to the second part of the proverb, it is said that work increases the value of a person, that is, for all people, it is said to show respect to hard-working, hardworking people, to stay away from lazy people, and to encourage them to be humane. After all, our forefathers emphasized in various examples how valuable water is for the life of humanity and nature, which is called "water of life" in folk proverbs.

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